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Abstract

A field experiment was conducted to estimate the genetic variability among Thirty-six germplasm line including three checks were sown in a RBD design with three replications, during Kharif - 2020 at Chilli and Vegetable Research Unit, Dr. PDKV, Akola. The observations were recorded on fourteen characters viz., Days to 50 per cent flowering, number of flowers per inflorescence, number of pods per inflorescence, days to first pod harvest, pod length(cm), pod width(cm), number of seeds per pod, mean pod weight(g), 100 dry seed weight(g), number of pods per plant, green pod yield per plant(g), green pod yield per plot(kg), Number of green pod picking and green fodder yield per plant (kg). The difference between GCV and PCV were less for all characters show that the influence of the environment on the trait (s) was very negligible. High estimates of GCV and PCV were observed for the characters green pod yield per plant, green pod yield per plot, number of green pod picking, number of pods per plant, number of flowers per inflorescence, number of pods per inflorescence, mean pod weight and pod length, pod width, green fodder yield. High heritability coupled with high genetic advance as per cent of mean was observed for all the characters except number of green pod picking indicating that these characters were governed by additive genes and selection will be rewarding for improvement of such traits.

Key words: Genetic Variability, *Dolichos bean*

Introduction

Dolichos bean is botanically known as *Dolichos lablab* L. "Dolichos" is a Greek word meaning "long" & "lablab" is an Arabic or Egyptian name meaning "dull rattle seed inside the dry pod". Vavilov (1939) has considered India as the primary centre of origin of Dolichos bean and wild forms are found in many parts of country. It is one of the most ancient among the cultivated plants and is presently grown throughout the tropical region of Asia, Africa and America (Purse glove, 1968). Formally Dolichos bean cultivated for its soft and edible pods and later the bean is cultivated for dry seed as pulse. It is mostly grown for human consumption and animal forage. The character for which variability is present should be highly heritable for the success of crop improvement program. The progress due to selection depends on heritability, selection intensity and genetic advance of the character. Heritability and genetic advance estimates for different targeted traits help the breeder to apply appropriate breeding methodology in the crop improvement program. Until now, very little attention is given by the workers on systematic crop improvement work of Dolichos bean. Hence, under the present investigation a systematic breeding programme has been initiated for exploiting the available genetic variability for development of consumer acceptable variety.

Material and Methods

The thirty six genotypes of Dolichos bean including three checks were grown in randomized block design with three replications in kharif - 2020. The observation were recorded for fourteen characters viz., days to 50 per cent flowering, number of flowers per inflorescence, number of pods per inflorescence, days to first pod harvest, pod length(cm), pod width(cm), number of seeds per pod, mean pod weight(g), 100 dry seed weight(g), number of pods per plant, green pod yield per plant(g), green pod yield per plot(kg), number of green pod picking and green fodder yield per plant (kg). All recommended agronomical practices were followed to better growth and health of crop. GCV, PCV and heritability were estimated by the formulae as suggested by Burton and Devane (1953).

Results and Discussion

The success of any crop improvement program will depend on existing genetic variability present in germplasm line. The analysis of variance for different characters, revealed highly significant differences among the genotypes both at five per cent and one per cent levels of significance, indicating sufficient amount of variability.

The extent of variability as measured by genotypic coefficient variation (GCV) and phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) provides

information regarding relative amount of variation in different characters. In the present study, close relationship between GCV and PCV was found in all the characters except green pod yield per plant, number of green pod picking and PCV values that were slightly greater than GCV and revealed a very little influence of environment for their expression. This was in confirmation with the results reported by Ganesh (2005), Upadhyay and Mehta (2011), Magalingam *et al.* (2013), Mohan *et al.* (2014) and Venkatesha *et al.* (2016), Radhelal *et al.* (2017).

The characters green pod yield per plant, green pod yield per plot, number of flowers per inflorescence, number of pods per plant, number of pods per inflorescence, mean pod weight, pod width and pod length showed higher estimates of GCV and PCV (Table 1). Similar kind of high estimates of variability were reported by Savitha (2008) for pod yield per plant, mean pod weight, Rai *et al.* (2009) for pod length and mean pod weight, Islam *et al.* (2011) for pod yield per plant, Upadhyay and Mehta (2011) for pod yield per plant, number of pods per inflorescence, mean pod weight and pod length, Magalingam *et al.* (2013) for pod weight, pod length and pod yield, Mohan *et al.* (2014) for pod yield per plant and pod length, Chaitanya *et al.* (2014) for the character like green pod yield per plant, number of pods per plant, Verma *et al.* (2015) for characters like number of pods per inflorescence, pod yield per plant, Choudhary *et al.* (2016) for pod yield per plant, pod yield per plot. Radhelal *et al.* (2017) for green pod yield per plant, green pod yield per plot. Comparatively high estimates of variability observed in the above characters especially green pod yield per plant and green pod yield per plot and mean pod weight shows that there is ample scope for selection.

The characters days to 50 per cent flowering, days to first pod harvest, 100 dry seed weight and number of seeds per pod showed moderate GCV and PCV values. These observations were in conformity with the findings of Rai *et al.* (2008) for days to 50 per cent flowering and number of grains per pod, Savitha (2008) for pod width and number of grains per pod, Low estimates of variability was observed for days to first pod harvest in the present study indicating little scope for selection. Similar kinds of findings were reported by Kambale *et al.* (2016).

All the growth, flower attributes, earliness attributes and pod attributes except had high genetic advance as per cent of mean coupled with high heritability estimates, indicating that these traits were under the strong influence of additive gene action and hence simple selection based on phenotypic performance of these traits would be more effective. This results were in agreement with Rai *et al.* (2008) for number of flowers per inflorescence, number of pods per inflorescence, pod length, pod

width and green pod yield per plant, Savitha (2008) for pod length, pod width, number of seeds per pods and pod yield per plant, Upadhyay and Mehta (2011) for green pod yield per plant, number of flower per inflorescence, number of pods per inflorescence, mean pod weight, pod length and pod width, Verma *et al.*, (2015) for all the characters except days to pod first harvest and pod width and Choudhary *et al.* (2016) for characters like pod yield per plant and pod width. Radhelal *et al.* (2017) for all characters except days to first pod harvest and number of seeds per pod. The medium heritability and high genetic advance as per cent mean values were observed for number green pod picking.

Similar kind of results have been reported in Dolichos bean by Radhelal *et al.* (2017) indicates the influence of additive gene action for these traits. These traits could be exploited through manifestation of additive components through selection. Hence, the breeder should adopt suitable breeding methodology to utilize additive gene effects, since varietal development will go a long way in the breeding programs, especially in case of Dolichos bean.

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Table 1. Components of genetic variability for different characters in Dolichos bean genotypes.

Sr No	Character	Range	General mean	Genotypic variance (σ^2_g)	Phenotypic variance (σ^2_p)	GCV (%)	PCV (%)	Heritability (BS) %	Genetic Advances	Genetic Advances as percent of mean (5 %)
1	Days to 50 percent flowering	47-171	137.7	558.06	564.40	17.15	17.24	98.87	48.45	35.17
2	Days to first pod harvest	64-182	150.2	417.14	421	13.59	13.67	99.08	41.84	27.86
3	Number of flowers per inflorescence	6.2-26.1	15.10	29.63	30.80	36.13	36.85	96.12	11.32	75.17
4	Number of pods per inflorescence	2.8-10.8	5.90	3.61	3.81	32.45	33.24	95.29	3.97	67.81
5	Pod length (cm)	5.02-16.92	9.67	10.25	10.30	33.11	33.19	99.48	6.54	67.70
6	Pod width (cm)	1.05-3.07	1.61	0.25	0.32	31.3	31.32	99.82	1.03	63.89
7	Number of seeds per pod	3.2-7.0	5.00	0.56	0.81	15.08	17.78	71.97	1.81	36.25
8	100 dry seed weight (g)	17.3-48.0	35.3	56.17	58.04	21.24	21.59	96.80	15.54	44.02
9	Mean pod weight (g)	1.8-15.9	8.20	13.95	14.00	45.37	45.42	99.57	7.63	92.72
10	Number pods per plant	33.78-424.52	135.70	6800.21	6874.12	60.78	61.11	98.92	169.08	124.62
11	Green Pod yield per plant (g)	127.3-1923.0	874.40	183325	242211	48.97	56.28	75.70	1003.70	114.78
12	Green Pod yield per plot (kg)	1.30 -19.23	8.70	18.34	24.22	48.97	56.28	75.69	10.03	114.78
13	Number of green pod picking	2.0-6.0	4.40	0.95	2.00	22.13	32.04	47.72	2.88	65.34
14	Green fodder yield (kg)	0.16-1.14	0.70	0.051	0.05	32.6	34.52	89.18	0.49	70.40